

**Analyzing the Experiences and Perceptions of Six African American Middle-Aged Men In
an Anonymous Maryland County Who Report Ongoing Childhood Sexual Abuse
(Case Study)**

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Abstract

In this grounded theory qualitative study, six African American men from an anonymous Maryland county, who reported being the victims of ongoing sexual assault during their childhood agreed to be interviewed and observed. For the purpose of participant protection, their identities have been kept anonymous and their specific demographics have been withheld. Each participant was interviewed one-on-one in a semi-structured interview. Observations were also done at times they were not aware that I was present in order to eliminate the observer effect as much as possible. Several themes emerged from the interviews and observations, including; toxic dynamics in the families of origin, being entrusted to people who had ulterior motives, stage setting for recurrent sexual abuse, familial revictimization, societal revictimization, perplexity regarding sexual identity, marital and/or relationship strains, and difficulty coping in other areas of life. Based on these themes, the theory that emerged was that “Middle-aged African American men who report toxic dynamics in the family of origin; sexual abuse; and experience revictimization may develop sexual addiction and/or sexual phobias. These men may also demonstrate difficulty in other areas of life functioning.”

Introduction

Dr. Martin Luther King, Jr. once made the statement that “our lives begin to end the day we become silent about things that matter.” By this, Dr. King was asserting that passivity regarding important issues will impact quality of life to the point that it brings about death more rapidly; presumably by living in a perpetual state of stress. Measuring activism on behalf of male sexual assault victims in the United States against this principle reveals that many lives have begun to end. This is due to the fact that 18% of all juvenile sexual assault victims are male (Victims of Sexual Violence: Statistics, 2024). While this may seem a small percentage, it only references the cases that are reported. It is currently unknown how many juvenile males are sexually assaulted and do not report it. While care for male victims has improved as evidenced by the creation of programs aimed specifically at helping them, there is work to be done as there is still a greater tendency regarding sexual assault to support female victims and treat male victims as an afterthought.

Furthermore, when it comes to the issue of sexual assault of male victims, African American males are at more of a disadvantage. Within the African American community, hip hop culture has been known to downplay the issue of sexual abuse of young boys by grown women as material for jokes (Sexual Abuse Taboo for Black Boys, 2009). It is likened to a rite of passage and considered “cool.” Many of these African American young men do not realize they have been abused sexually and By contrast, male victims of sexual abuse at the hands of another male usually do not talk about it due to shame. Complicating the issue more is that “Black boys who are sexually abused rarely if ever tell anyone, and silence continues into adulthood (Rhodes, 2022). This robs many African American male victims of critical opportunities for healing.

Background

Not so long ago, sexual abuse of men was not treated as a crime across the world. In fact, it was not until 1994 that rape of a man was recognized as a crime in English law (Thomas & Kopel, 2023). Instead, a crime called buggery was prosecuted for this sort of offense and it carried a much more lenient penalty than rape. Even in 1997, health clinics had nothing in place to help male victims. Some clinic personnel were quoted as making statements such as “we don’t do men,” and “most men who were sodomized wanted it to happen.” Misconceptions such as these prevented many men from seeking help during this time.

As many as 1 in 6 victims of sexual abuse are male. (Houghton et al, 2023). What is more is that many male victims never report the abuse. Some reasons for this are shame, fear, societal perceptions of masculinity, misconceptions about the meaning of arousal during sexual assault, and the gender of the perpetrator regardless of it being male or female. One may logically conclude from this information that the aforementioned statistics are an underrepresentation of the true number of male victims of sexual assault.

Furthermore, popularized myths that surround the sexual abuse of males contribute to the societal downplay of this issue. One such myth is that only gay guys are sexually assaulted (Men and Sexual Assault, 2024). This myth has been reported as being one of the major reasons that many male victims do not come forward when sexually assaulted. Another reported myth is that males cannot be abused by women. This myth has also been reported as a reason that a great many males who are sexually assaulted do not tell.

Problem

Much research has been done on the sexual assault of male victims. However, many of these studies have examined the issue of sexual abuse of young males as well as adult males. Very few studies have focused exclusively on the experiences and perceptions of middle-aged, African American men who report ongoing sexual abuse as children. Thus, this case study aimed to analyze the perceptions that have been engendered by sexual abuse during the formative years of the men in this study.

Research Questions

The following research questions were addressed in this study: a.) What were the experiences of middle-aged men who report sexual abuse in early childhood? b.) What perceptions do these men hold with respect to the abuse? c.) What do their perceptions show?

Research Methodology

Participant Selection

Participants were selected using random sampling. These men were participants in a group for men who reported being abused sexually as children. The aim of this group was to help these and the other twenty male participants to “navigate their paths to healing” through the sharing of their collective experiences; their own personal strategies for achieving healing; and support one another on their respective journeys. Of the participants asked to take part in this study, six of them expressed willingness.

Data Collection

For the purpose of achieving triangulation, two methods of data collection were used. First, information was completed through the use of semi-structured interviews. These interviews focused on the participants’ experiences with sexual abuse in their formative years

and sexual behaviors later on in life. Additionally, information was gleaned through the use of direct observation as a way of examining and analyzing how study participants function in daily life.

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed via a grounded theory approach. Using the totality of the participant responses, themes became apparent based on reported perceptions and experiences. Once the interviews were conducted, the participants were observed directly during a snippet of their daily functioning to determine if themes from the interview were supported by the observation and/or if other themes became available. In order to maintain an objective and unbiased perspective, only background information was examined and a literature review was excluded for the purpose of theory formation.

Results/Themes

Based on the interviews and observations, multiple themes became evident that may explain why these participants were exposed to abuse on an ongoing basis. These themes included toxic dynamics in the families of origin, which led to their being entrusted to people who had ulterior motives. By entrusting their children to these people, these parents set the stage for recurrent sexual abuse. Through the validation and/or criminalization of the victims' experiences, both the family and society had a hand in revictimizing the participants. This led to life difficulties such as perplexity regarding sexual identity, marital and/or relationship strains, and difficulty coping in other areas of life.

Toxic Dynamics in the Family of Origin

All participants in this study reported toxic families of origin in which one of several dynamics were present. One such family type was characterized by authoritarian

parents/caretakers who were overly strict. At the polar opposite extreme was laissez-faire parenting, in which the parents/caretakers took no active interest in the lives of the children whose care they were responsible for. In some cases, elements of both dynamics were present. Mainly this dynamic took place in two parent homes and/or homes in which extended families were living together, both of which demonstrated a dynamic in which one parent/caretaker assumed a more dominant role and utilized this power negatively. Evidence for this is seen in following statements made by participants in the study.

Authoritarian Parenting Dynamics	Laissez-Faire Parenting Dynamics
When I was at home, it was all chaos. My mother was manipulative, so anything she said went. She had many ways of getting what she wanted. We didn't dare cross or question her. (Participant 1)	My father was always out cheating on my mother. My father couldn't be bothered to question her, he was busy sneaking around with all those women. (Participant 1)
I was always afraid to tell my aunt thinking I would get in trouble. She did love me, but she was very strict. Too strict at times. (Participant 2)	At the same time, my mother had a drinking problem and I was made to feel responsible for helping her and caring for her. (Participant 2)
My father was not in my life a lot and when he did come around, it was to "scare me straight." He told me I would be dead by 21 because I acted out a lot in school. (Participant 3)	My mother was a single mother and there were many times I was left in the care of my neighbor, a woman my mother knew so she could go out and do her own thing. (Participant 3)
Mom said it was her friend's son's birthday. Even though I was tired, I went, not really that I wanted to, but when I asked my mother if I could sit this one out, she said no. And that was the end of that. When my mom spoke, that was it. (Participant 5)	My foster father was one who allowed us a great deal of freedom, but it often came with a price. We had to be home by a certain time, so we could eat and get ready for bed. And anyone who ran late would make it so that none of us could go outside and do our own thing the next day. So we made sure everyone was in the house when he said to be. (Participant 4)
This uncle was not a stupid man either. He always made sure he was right nearby me, watching me. If I ever talked to a stranger or tried to make a friend, I was severely punished (mainly beaten). (Participant 6)	When I turned 15, it stopped after my mother was released from jail and I begged the judge to allow me to return to her. The abuse from my uncle stopped, but I was all messed up. I told my mother about it, and she told me to forget about it and let it go because he had taken care of me. She said it was just how he was and other family members had been through it too from him, not just me. She said it was something they knew they had to deal with because he had money and their parents couldn't afford to take care of them. (Participant 6)

Table 1.1

“Participant Responses Indicating the Specific, Toxic Family Dynamic in The Family of Origin”

Being Entrusted to People with Ulterior Motives, Setting the Stage for Ongoing Abuse

In both categories, the participants’ home life contributed directly to their abuse as those with parents who were authoritarian gave them no choice in who they went/stayed with.

Likewise, those who reported laissez-faire parenting, were given to any adult who wanted to take them. The evidence for this is in the statements made by these participants in Table 1.2

Participant	Entrusted to People With Ulterior Motives, Setting the Stage for Abuse
1	That’s my earliest memory. I was taken out by my aunts who kept me for the night. I was forced to perform sex acts with them. This took place from the time I was 6 until 18.
2	a.) My first memory of being abused sexually was at the age of 4. I didn’t know everything that was happening. Even though I don’t remember everything about the abuse, I remember being in bed, naked with this woman who my aunt trusted to watch me. I was naked and the way she touched me, I felt a hot sensation in my genitals. The only thing I remember her telling me is to lay down. b.) As I got older, the abuse progressed. The woman abusing me began opening up to me like I was her husband, sharing inappropriate things with me. I felt obligated to care for her since she was clearly having a hard time in life.
3	a.) I was left in the care of my neighbor, a woman my mother knew, so she could go out and do her own thing. All kinds of people were in and out of her house. I was constantly molested by men and women; b.) I was left in the care of my neighbor, a woman my mother knew, so she could go out and do her own thing. All kinds of people were in and out of her house. I was constantly molested by men and women. c.) At age 10, there was a woman in my neighborhood my mom knew, who I had sex with on the regular. I didn’t wanna do it, but she was determined. d.) When I fathered a child by [this woman] at age 12, I was never the same.
4	a.) When I was 5, my mother died suddenly and I was taken and put into foster care; b.) [My foster father] would put drugs in my food that would leave me in a deep sleep; c.) I would often wake up to my pants being pulled down or him masturbating me. d.) Sometimes he would have other foster kids perform sex acts on me. e.) I couldn’t fight back because the drugs were too strong, making it hard for me to move.
5	a.) When I got to the party, Mom’s friend’s son was excited to see me. His uncles were there along with some friends and a few of his cousins. That night, when I fell asleep, being tired, I was abruptly awoken. His uncles said since I was the first one asleep, they were going to “get” me. Two of them held me down, one pulled my pants down and they took turns fondling me. They even called the other boys over there and watch them do it; b.) After that day, I was molested by male and female cousins/family friends over the course of the years of my life. It felt like they could sense what had happened to me, detect my fear, and took advantage of it.
6	a.) From the time I was 7 until I was 14, I was raped by my uncle. My father was never in my life and my mother was locked up. b.) My uncle claimed he didn’t want me lost in the system. c.) He would come into my room at night and have sex me.

Table 2.1

“Participant Responses About Being Entrusted to Others and the Setting of the Stage for the Abuse to Be Ongoing”

Familial Revictimization

Many participants reported that the toxic family dynamics, which put them in the hands of those who abused them, led to their being further victimized at the hands of those in their families. For some of them, it was family members who validated the abuse by telling them it was a good thing that it happened when it was female on male sexual assault. Others however reported the downplaying of their experiences with sexual abuse when it was male-on-male. There was a third group, whose familial revictimization was less obvious as their families had set dynamics that created breakdowns in their feeling free to communicate with their caretakers. This was due to authoritarianism in parenting, which made them afraid to tell their parents. Several quotes from interviews with these participants demonstrate this principle.

Validation of Abuse	Downplaying of Abuse	Fear of parents/caretakers
I can remember getting several pats on the backs from uncles when I tried to tell them about the abuse because I wanted it to stop. They talked about what a positive experience it was for me. (Participant 2)	When I turned 15, it stopped after my mother was released from jail and I begged the judge to allow me to return to her. The abuse from my uncle stopped, but I was all messed up. I told my mother about it, and she told me to forget about it and let it go because he had taken care of me. She said it was just how he was and other family members had been through it too from him, not just me. She said it was something they knew they had to deal with because he had money and their parents couldn't afford to take care of them. (Participant 6)	I was always afraid to tell my aunt thinking I would get in trouble. She did love me, but she was very strict. Too strict at times. (Participant 2)
When I told my father, he high fived me and told me to consider myself a true man now for having had such an experience. This left me more shaken up and confused. (Participant 3)		I never told because I thought I would get punished. (Participant 5)

Table 2.2

“Participant Perceptions Indicating Familial Revictimization”

Societal Revictimization

Compounding this issue of familial revictimization was the fact that society also had a hand in revictimizing those who were victims of ongoing sexual abuse. This took place in one of three ways. One participant reported being blamed for the abuse. Another reported having a friend validate the abuse. Others spoke of trying to do what they could to hide it from society. This may be explained by the negative treatment of a misinformed society during this time concerning the nature of male sexual abuse. There are quotes from the participants that shed more light on this aspect of their experiences with sexual abuse.

Victim Blaming	Validating the Abuse	Hiding Behind Societal Norms
<p>One day, I was bold enough to tell an adult I trusted. Her response to me was that I should have stopped it, unless I pretended to be asleep, knowing what they would do to me, and enjoying it. (Participant 5)</p>	<p>I once told a trusted friend, who high fived me and told me I was “the man”. (Participant 3)</p> <p>I became very promiscuous, looking constantly for my next “fix.” Having sex with girls my age was like a drug to me. To my friends, I was like some kind of a god. (Participant 1)</p> <p>During my high school years, I began looking to have sex as much as I could. I was real popular too. (Participant 2)</p>	<p>For the longest, I [expletive omitted] as many women as I could to “prove” my masculinity. I felt like if I didn’t, people would see right through me. (Participant 4)</p> <p>My goal then became to prove how masculine I was. I started having sex with a lot of girls my age. Secretly, I wanted to be with other guys. (Participant 6)</p>

Table 2.3

“Participant Responses Indicating Societal Revictimization”

Perplexity Regarding Sexual Identity

Several participants reported perplexity regarding their sexual identities. Their perplexities and attempts to hide aspects of their sexuality that made them uncomfortable, may be explained by the familial and societal factors that revictimized them. One participant reported dealing with unwanted homosexual urges. Two other participants reported that their sex

lives were unfulfilling as they wanted nothing to do with sex and would be totally comfortable with celibacy.

Participant	Information Communicated	What it Reveals
3	<p>“Most of my sexual relationships now are with men. I do have a girlfriend too.”</p> <p>“ I’m not in a rush, but if she turns out to be the right woman, I would marry her.”</p> <p>“ I like men and women, it’s just between the two of them, I like men more, sexually.”</p>	<p>Participant 3 may be bisexual with a stronger preference for men than women. While he has not dismissed the idea of marrying his girlfriend if she is the “right one,” he seems to be comfortable with presenting the information about his girlfriend publicly. However, his preference for men is something he does not share publicly. This indicates that he may be at odds with himself over who he is sexually and/or still be hiding his true feelings from a society that was less tolerant in the past as he has had to do for survival.</p>
4	<p>“For the longest, I [expletive omitted] as many women as I could to “prove” my masculinity. I felt like if I didn’t, people would see right through me.”</p> <p>“Today, my sex life is strained and the very thought of sex disgusts me.”</p>	<p>Participant 4 may be totally put off at the idea of sexual contact of any type due to his traumatic past. At one point, when he was being molested, he was drugged to the point that he could not defend himself. Then, he felt forced by societal expectation to have sex with as many girls as he could. Now, he has become more honest with himself. Being as though sexual contact has always been traumatic to him, he wants no part of it.</p>
5	<p>“I was confused because I had an erection and felt a sensation in my genitals I had never felt before.”</p> <p>“Today, this abuse has made my sex life difficult. I have been married three times and have 3 kids. Sex is always uncomfortable to me, the thought of it makes me anxious. I only do it to please my wife. We have sex about twice a week. “</p>	<p>This participant may experience conflicting feelings as a result of his having become aroused during the sexual abuse. On one hand, he very clearly loves his wife and wants to please her. Still, he is uncomfortable with the thought or act of sex.</p>
6	<p>“My goal then became to prove how masculine I was. I started having sex with a lot of girls my age. Secretly, I wanted to be with other guys.”</p> <p>“When I was 21, I met one woman who gave me such good sex, I thought I couldn’t live without her. I married her. We had 3 children. I cheated on her with a lot of women.”</p> <p>“ Each time I felt like I wanted to do something with another guy, I slept with a bunch of different women to prove to myself I was a man.”</p> <p>“My marriage did not last and I continue to struggle with wanting to sleep with other men. I keep sleeping with a lot of women in spite of this.”</p>	<p>This participant may be experiencing discomfort with his true sexuality. While he only is ever intimate with women, he constantly craves and fantasizes about sexual activity with other men. He goes to extra lengths to prove that he is heterosexual. This may be explained by the attitude of society toward male sexual abuse due to a lack of information.</p>

Table 2.4

“Responses Indicating Perplexity About One’s Sexuality”

Relationship/Marriage Difficulties

Another theme associated with the middle-aged African American men who report ongoing sexual abuse in childhood is difficulty in marriage/relationships. Some participant responses demonstrated difficulty with remaining faithful to their partners. This may be explained by the fact that those who experienced difficulty with being faithful reported an obsession with sex. At the opposite extreme, some participants who were married/in relationships reported phobias or irrational fears around sex with their partners, which may be explained by the trauma they have come to associate with sexual intimacy.

Sexual Compulsion Resulting from Obsession	Sexual Repulsion Resulting from Phobia
When I found out she was pregnant, she and I married. That was a big mistake. I mean I was someone who loved sex and I did cheat on her, but she tried to ruin my life. (Participant 1)	Today, my sex life is strained and the very thought of sex disgusts me. This is why my wife and I separated. (Participant 4)
I am in marriage number three because I cheated on the first two and I'm determined to stay faithful. I've gotten sick of women using sex against me. It destroyed my first two marriages. (Participant 2)	Today, this abuse has made my sex life difficult. I have been married three years and have 3 kids. Sex is always uncomfortable to me, the thought of it makes me anxious. I only do it to please my wife. We have sex about twice a week. (Participant 5)

Table 2.5

“Participants Reporting Strained Marriages/Relationships”

Difficulty Coping in Other Areas of Life

In addition to the sexual and relational difficulties revealed, the direct observations revealed other areas of difficulty in the participants' lives. In order to ensure accurate results, I obtained each participant's consent to observe them at times when they did not know I was present. Each one gave me permission. And to protect their dignity, I wrote down several direct observations from the same place that all clearly showed the same theme. Participants were allowed to select the one they were most comfortable with me sharing. The responses

demonstrated several difficulties with coping with stressful situations. These difficulties included angry outbursts ; codependency; and overcompensation. Each of these may be explained by feelings of inadequacy created by the years of sexual and presumably other types of abuse.

Theme	Observation(s)	Potential Explanation
<p>Angry outbursts</p>	<p>a.) Participant 1 “took the bait” when his ex-wife behaved in an antagonistic manner toward him. His reaction was very abrupt and angry. It was characteristic of someone who had been holding back a lot of anger and felt pushed too far; b.) When one of the council members snapped back at Participant 4 saying that he was trying to tell her what was in her mind, his actions indicated that he was triggered. He retorted with “I can answer that easily, not a damn thing! You’re part of the problem! I don’t know why the hell they elected you. But if I have a say, you can bet your ass you won’t be reelected!” Next, he proceeded to leave. When he was out of the meeting, he said “BITCH!” just loud enough for the councilwoman and attendants to hear him.</p>	<p>While both participants’ reactions may appear unconnected to the sexual abuse; they actually may be very thematically connected. In each participant’s case, the reaction may be thematically related to the lack of control each experienced in their families of origin that ultimately led to the sexual abuse of an ongoing nature.</p> <p>In the case of Participant 1, he may have been triggered by a reminder of being forced by his mother to do everything she told him to do and “exploded” as an attempt to “reclaim power”. This is thematically related to the sexual abuse because he had no choice in the matter of going with his aunts, who sexually abused him, and became addicted to sex. As a result, it has been used against him many times and he is triggered.</p> <p>In the case of Participant 4, he was given a lot of freedom during his childhood, except when he was drugged. During this lack of control, things were done to him against his will despite his protests. His reaction is related thematically because he likely felt unheard despite his protests at the Town Hall meeting. Hence, he reacted as he wanted to react to his abusers from his childhood.</p>
<p>Codependency</p>	<p>a.) With respect to Participant 2, he came across codependent as he had lunch with some friends. While he came across as being the one his friends turned to for advice, it seemed like more than being advice or a conversation, his word was treated like law. If he advised against it, they listened. If he advised for it, they listened. In one instance, his friend showed obvious signs of intoxication, and he calmly took his friend’s drink, poured it in the sink beside their table, and told the bartender to cut him off. It was very clear that he was in charge in</p>	<p>a.) His codependency may be linked to his past sexual abuse based on the fact that his abuser began to open up to him as though he were her husband. She made him feel responsible for taking care of her and his being a 13-years-old, he was easily manipulated. As a result, he continues to play the role of caretaker as he feels it is his way of having control. This may explain why he has chosen friends who demonstrate emotional instability. The sexual abuse he suffered in his formative years by the woman who manipulated him into playing caretaker may have created in him a need to be needed. b.) In the case of Participant 5, this codependency may be explained by the fact</p>

	<p>that social setting. He had friends who needed him, and he was comfortable in being in the caretaking role. b.) Participant 5 had company and had one “friend” who was rude to him, made snide remarks, and complained about multiple things, the food that was being served, the fact that he did not have any liquor, and the quality of the gathering. Ignoring how this “friend” was acting, he continued to treat him kindly and went out of his way to be gracious.</p>	<p>that he felt somewhat validated by his abusers who while they were doing unhealthy things to him, they made him feel wanted. His feeling unwanted by someone claiming to be a friend may have caused him to go to desperate measures to get it back as it represented his desire for validation.</p>
<p>Overcompensation</p>	<p>a.) Participant 3 was observed downplaying his abuse by making jokes that he asked not be used in the study. While his comments came across as witty and perfectly timed, it was inconsistent with the pain portrayed in the interview; b.) . Participant 6 was observed posting content that was sexually explicit/</p>	<p>a.) For Participant 3, this may be explained by a perceived need to overcompensate for feelings of inadequacy through downplaying them using humor. This is thematically related to his sexual abuse as he seems to be trying to do what he perceives is expected of a man. This thought may have been brought on by his father and friend’s validation of his abuser; b.) Participant 6’s use of sexually explicit material on social media may be explained by his unwanted homosexual urges and his desire to dissociate from them.</p>

Table 3.1

“Observations and Their Potential Explanations”

Conclusions

All things considered, the participants in this study have developed unhealthy self concepts from a multitude of factors over which they had no control. For one, those in authoritarian families had no choice in the matter of going with the people their parents selected and trusted. They feared they would not be believed because the adults presented a united front, enabling the abuse to continue. Those in neglectful families had no one to turn to, making it easy to continue perpetrating the abuse. Additionally, the lengthy nature of the abuse could explain why relationship issues abounded in each of these cases. Furthermore, the family’s responses validating the female on male abuse were harmful and invalidating. When the victim was told how he should feel about it, he felt unheard and invalidated. Moreover, societal responses

validating the female on male abuse was harmful and reiterated to the male victim that he was wrong for feeling like he did, revictimizing him. Also, societal responses that accused the victim, indicating that he must have been enjoying it were disparaging and revictimizing to him. As a result, when several participants attempted to be involved in meaningful relationships with female partners, they experienced a host of problems from perceived inability to remain faithful, to craving same sex intimacy, to being repulsed and scared at the thought of sexual intimacy. Adding to that was that each participant's difficulty with coping in life was evident in their stress responses, which related thematically to their sexual abuse as angry outbursts, codependency, and overcompensation, all of which are defense mechanisms were observed.

Theory

Based on the information collected from the interviews and direct observations in this study, the theory that emerged is that middle-aged African American men who report toxic dynamics in the family of origin; sexual abuse; and experience revictimization may develop sexual addiction and/or sexual phobias. These men may also demonstrate difficulty in other areas of life functioning. This is evidenced by the fact that each of the men in this study when interviewed and observed gave responses and showed behaviors that were consistent with the aforementioned factors. From their early childhood, the stage was set for abuse to occur and continue as it remained unchecked. Moreover, familial and/or societal factors were mentioned by all participants as having a detrimental effect and revictimizing the participant.

Recommendations

Several recommendations would help make the content of this study more useful. Firstly, it is advisable that this study be repeated on a larger scale to ensure that these results are more generalizable. Additionally, it is advisable that educational opportunities be created in the

community of this anonymous Maryland county and eventually across the United States to educate people on the way that ongoing sexual abuse can get started and how to stop the cycle should they recognize it. Moreover, it is advisable that those involved in any aspect of mental health, who work with African American men who report being victims of sexual abuse, utilize this information to inform their decisions about the best strategies for helping these men overcome any challenges they may be experiencing.

Limitations

One limitation to this study is its small sample size. The fact that six men were selected at random to participate may limit the generalizability of this study to the African American male population as a whole. Moreover, resources were a limitation in this study as being self-funded limited access to some resources that may have enabled me to conduct this study on a larger scale.

Delimitation

The delimitation is that this study was restricted to middle age African American men in the anonymous Maryland County, excluding anyone who does not meet all criteria. This was necessary as this is a group that I have found to be less studied than other groups.

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Appendix A:

Participant Experience Matrix

Interview Questions & Responses of Middle Age Men Who Report Being Sexually Abused as Children

Participant	Please tell anything you are comfortable sharing about the sexual abuse you reported.	How are you feeling as you discuss these things?
<p>1</p> <p>45-y-o</p>	<p>It started when I was 6 years old. That’s my earliest memory. I was taken out by my aunts who kept me for the night. I was forced to perform sex acts with them. This took place from the time I was 6 until 18. When I was at home it was all chaos. My father was always out cheating on my mother. My mother was manipulative, so anything she said went. She had many ways of getting what she wanted. We didn’t dare cross or question her. My father couldn’t be bothered to question her, he was busy sneaking around with all those women. Then I married a woman just like her.</p> <p>I became very promiscuous, looking constantly for my next “fix.” Having sex with girls my age was like a drug to me. To my friends, I was like some kind of a god.</p> <p>My wife was my good friend from high school. While we never dated in high school, we became lovers in college, and when I found out she was pregnant, she and I married. That was a big mistake. I mean I was someone who loved sex and I did cheat on her, but she tried to ruin my life.</p>	<p>Man this hurts. I’m just glad somebody is finally listening to me. Nothing I say matters. It never has to my family, my wife, or anyone else. Now, they’re on her side.</p> <p>(Participant shook and cried as he discussed this portion).</p>
<p>2</p> <p>44-y-o</p>	<p>My first memory of being abused sexually was at the age of 4. I didn’t know everything that was happening. Even though I don’t remember everything about the abuse, I remember being in bed, naked with this woman who my aunt trusted to watch me. I was naked and the way she touched me, I felt a hot sensation in my genitals. The only thing I remember her telling me is to lay down. I was always afraid to tell my aunt thinking I would get in trouble. She did love me, but she was very strict. Too strict at times. As I got older, the abuse progressed. The woman abusing me began opening up to me like I was her husband, sharing inappropriate things with me. I felt obligated to care for her since she was clearly having a hard time in life. At the same time, my mother had a drinking problem and I was made to feel responsible for helping her and caring for her. I can remember getting several pats on the backs from uncles when I tried to tell them about the abuse because I wanted it to stop. They talked about what a positive experience it was for me.</p> <p>During my high school years, I began looking to have sex as much as I could. I was real popular too. One woman</p>	<p>It really does help me to talk about this. I feel like I’ve kept it bottled up for so long. Sometimes though I feel like I’m that child I was when the abuse was going on, not the adult I am today.</p>

	<p>tried to trap me with a baby when I was 16. Today, I have 5 children, and 3 baby's mothers. I am in marriage number three because I cheated on the first two and I'm determined to stay faithful. I've gotten sick of women using sex against me. It destroyed my first two marriages.</p>	
<p>3 46-y-o</p>	<p>My mother was a single mother and there were many times I was left in the care of my neighbor, a woman my mother knew, so she could go out and do her own thing. All kinds of people were in and out of her house. I was constantly molested by men and women. My father was not in my life a lot and when he did come around, it was to "scare me straight." He told me I would be dead by 21 because I acted out a lot in school. It was because I needed help. I kept being sexually abused and I felt I couldn't tell my mother.</p> <p>At age 10, there was a woman in my neighborhood my mom knew, who I had sex with on the regular. I didn't wanna do it, but she was determined. When I told my father, he high fived me and told me to consider myself a true man now for having had such an experience. This left me more shaken up and confused. I once told a trusted friend, who high fived me and told me I was "the man".</p> <p>When I fathered a child by her at age 12, I was never the same. Most of my sexual relationships now are with men. I do have a girlfriend too. I'm not in a rush, but if she turns out to be the right woman, I would marry her. I like men and women, it's just between the two of them, I like men more, sexually.</p>	<p>It's bringing back a lot of painful memories. It's not easy. But if I can help somebody else, I will.</p>
<p>4 42-y-o</p>	<p>When I was 5, my mother died suddenly and I was taken and put into foster care. My foster father was one who allowed us a great deal of freedom, but it often came with a price. We had to be home by a certain time, so we could eat and get ready for bed. And anyone who ran late would make it so that none of us could go outside and do our own thing the next day. So we made sure everyone was in the house when he said to be. He would put drugs in my food that would leave me in a deep sleep. I would often wake up to my pants being pulled down or him masturbating me. Sometimes he would have other foster kids perform sex acts on me. I couldn't fight back because the drugs were too strong, making it hard for me to move.</p> <p>For the longest, I [expletive omitted] as many women as I could to "prove" my masculinity. I felt like if I didn't, people would see right through me. Today, my sex life is strained and the very thought of sex disgusts me. This is why my wife and I separated. I am protective over my children to a fault and I do not want them to go through what I went through.</p>	<p>Talking about it helps some. It helps me. But at the same time, I feel like I did when it was happening and I get anxious and fearful.</p>

<p>5 41-y-o</p>	<p>It was Spring Break and I was 9. I had spent my whole weekend with my godparents. When I got home, I thought I would get to go in my own space and take a break and just rest. Mom said it was her friend’s son’s birthday. Even though I was tired, I went, not really that I wanted to, but when I asked my mother if I could sit this one out, she said no. And that was the end of that. When my mom spoke, that was it.</p> <p>When I got to the party, Mom’s friend’s son was excited to see me. His uncles were there along with some friends and a few of his cousins. That night, when I fell asleep, being tired, I was abruptly awoken. His uncles said since I was the first one asleep, they were going to “get” me. Two of them held me down, one pulled my pants down and they took turns fondling me. They even called the other boys over there and watch them do it.</p> <p>I was confused because I had an erection and felt a sensation in my genitals I had never felt before. When I looked scared, they stopped, told me they were sorry and just playing a prank.</p> <p>After that day, I was molested by male and female cousins/family friends over the course of the years of my life. It felt like they could sense what had happened to me, detect my fear, and took advantage of it. I never told because I thought I would get punished.</p> <p>One day, I was bold enough to tell an adult I trusted. Her response to me was that I should have stopped it, unless I pretended to be asleep, knowing what they would do to me, and enjoying it.</p> <p>Today, this abuse has made my sex life difficult. I have been married three years and have 3 kids. Sex is always uncomfortable to me, the thought of it makes me anxious. I only do it to please my wife. We have sex about twice a week.</p>	<p>I feel shame, fear, anger, and sadness as I talk about this. Thinking about what happened to me makes me feel like I’m somehow responsible. I know with my mind that I am not, but my heart can’t tell that. But I do feel more peace finally being able to tell someone.</p>
<p>6 44-y-o</p>	<p>From the time I was 7 until I was 14, I was raped by my uncle. My father was never in my life and my mother was locked up. My uncle claimed he didn’t want me lost in the system. He would come into my room at night and have sex me. This uncle was not a stupid man either. He always made sure he was right nearby me, watching me. If I ever talked to a stranger or tried to make a friend, I was severely punished (mainly beaten).</p> <p>When I turned 15, it stopped after my mother was released from jail and I begged the judge to allow me to return to her. The abuse from my uncle stopped, but I was all messed up. I told my mother about it, and she told me to forget about it and let it go because he had taken care of me. She said it was just how he was and other family members had been through it too from him, not just me. She said it was something they knew they had to deal with because he had money and their parents couldn’t afford to take care of them.</p> <p>My goal then became to prove how masculine I was. I started having sex with a lot of girls my age. Secretly, I wanted to be</p>	<p>I’ve never told anyone this. I feel relieved after finally telling someone. But man, the thought of what he did to me, messes with my mind. It’s like I feel conflicted. When I have sex with women, I like doing it. I have however given in to my sexual urges for other men and slept with them too.</p>

	<p>with other guys.</p> <p>When I was 21, I met one woman who gave me such good sex, I thought I couldn't live without her. I married her. We had 3 children. I cheated on her with a lot of women. Each time I felt like I wanted to do something with another guy, I slept with a bunch of different women to prove to myself I was a man. My marriage did not last and I continue to struggle with wanting to sleep with other men. I keep sleeping with a lot of women in spite of this.</p>	
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Appendix B:

Direct Observation of Participants-

***They all gave me their schedules so they would not know when I was going to show up and to remove or minimize the observer effect. All agreed to this and with my having made multiple observations, all were allowed to pick the one they were most comfortable with me sharing.**

Participant	Observed Behaviors
1	Participant 1 was observed during a 5:00 pm pick up of his children from his ex-wife at the police station. When the children went with him, his somber expression became more happy. His ex-wife used this as a time to serve him court papers for child support. He became enraged and first stated that he was already paying child support. Her behavior was antagonistic toward him as she reiterated that she was a woman, she would get what she wanted. He began shouting enraged statements at her and the police who were nearby instructed him that he was to leave immediately.
2	Participant 2 was observed on a night out with several of his friends. He had previously given his wife permission to share his location with me so that I could observe him undetected. When he was out with his friends for drinks, he hung out with people whose personalities were kind, yet they lacked self confidence. He acted in the role of a caretaker to these people. They often sought his input on decisions about whether or not to approach certain women they were interested in, whom they saw in the bar. More than being advice or a conversation, his word was treated like law. If he advised against it, they listened. If he advised for it, they listened. In one instance, his friend showed obvious signs of intoxication, and he calmly took his friend's drink, poured it in the sink beside their table, and told the bartender to cut him off. It was very clear that he was in charge in that social setting. He had friends who needed him, and he was comfortable in being in the caretaking role.
3	Participant 3 was observed during a 12-step meeting in which he and some fellow Christians were working on processing their past pain. To reduce the chances of the observer effect occurring, I attended every meeting and did not disclose to him which meeting I would use as my direct observation. When discussing his past pain, he was very forthcoming. He gave details about the abuse, he told of ways he was working the steps;

	<p>including; journaling, praying, and surrounding himself with positive people. As he discussed his traumatic experiences, which were relevant to the night's topic, he infused humor into what he said. While the group demonstrated receptiveness toward his humor, his microexpression which lasted no more than 2 seconds was one of sadness s he frowned and slightly furrowed his brow.</p>
<p>4</p>	<p>The participant was observed directly during a town hall meeting, which he did not know I was present for. He was very direct in the presence of the local politicians. When he stood to speak, he articulated his thoughts very passionately. He stated that he was sick of the lack of police presence in his neighborhood where he and his children live. He went on to describe conditions that make him uncomfortable for his children to have to walk to and from school in. His most vocal opposition was regarding the fact that he pays to live here and he felt the council members did not take his or other neighbors' concerns seriously. When one of the council members snapped back at him, saying that he was trying to tell her what was in her mind, his actions indicated that he was triggered. He retorted with "I can answer that easily, not a damn thing! You're part of the problem! I don't know why the hell they elected you. But if I have a say, you can bet your ass you won't be reelected!" Next, he proceeded to leave. When he was out of the meeting, he said "BITCH!" just loud enough for the councilwoman and attendants to hear him. Some wore concerned expressions, others reacted with amusement.</p>
<p>5</p>	<p>Participant 5 was observed during one evening when I visited him. To reduce the chance of the observer effect, I did not share when I would use the visit as an observation nor what I was specifically looking for. On this particular day, he had invited some friends over. He and his friends engaged in friendly banter and then began playing a game of Spades.</p> <p>He had one "friend" who was rude to him, made snide remarks, and complained about multiple things, the food that was being served, the fact that he did not have any liquor, and the quality of the gathering. Ignoring how this "friend" was acting, he continued to treat him kindly and went out of his way to be gracious. It was not until another friend who did not know this friend spoke up and told the rude guest to "shut the hell up," that Participant 5 felt emboldened in saying that he did not appreciate how he was being spoken to. He later shared with me that this was someone he knew from a class they were both taking, He reasoned that he just "paid him no attention when he was drunk."</p>

6	Without adequate opportunity to observe him in person, I obtained permission from him to use his Instagram page to determine any other themes. The content on his Instagram page consisted of three topics; sexually suggestive pictures of women, memes expressing why “trifling women” had difficulty finding good men, and pictures of himself with his arms around scantily dressed women in different locations.
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